

CDCC Community Engagement Framework

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A collaboration between CCPH, DCRI, and UNC-CHER

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CDCC COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT FRAMEWORK

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RADx-UP, as NIH's single largest investment in health disparities research, brings together institutions and communities in partnership to connect underserved communities to needed resources and COVID-19 testing. As a centralized source of support for the more than 125 RADx-UP projects conducting [community-engaged research](#), it is important for the CDCC to ensure internal leadership and staff are well informed and equipped with the knowledge and skills necessary to support community-engaged research. As CDCC supports these projects, it is important that it models community-engaged approaches.

In early 2021, the Community Engagement Core initiated meetings with CDCC leadership and staff, as well as RADx-UP academic and [community](#) partners, to better understand their needs and observations around community engagement. These meetings and listening sessions provided insight that spoke to the need for guidelines to support CDCC's efforts to build a culture of engagement. Across these meetings, similar needs emerged:

A standard definition of community engagement

Best practices to support cores as they apply community-engaged approaches to their work

Guiding principles to inform the work of the CDCC

In response, the Community Engagement Core developed this framework to help guide CDCC leadership and staff in their work. While this guide serves as an internal working document, view this as a guide to support interactions, processes, initiatives, etc. both internally and externally, recognizing that the audience will vary depending on the situation or need. Also, acknowledging that some work will require more layered approaches as your audience may involve both internal and external [partners](#) or [stakeholders](#) at different steps of the process.

Keep in Mind

This document is fluid. As you work to implement best practices identified in this guide, make sure to take note of challenges, successes, and/or additional best practices identified during your work. There will be evaluative check-ins 4, 8, and 12 months post-implementation. Nevertheless, if you need support in the interim, feel free to reach out to CCPH for support. As you work to incorporate more community-engaged approaches in your work, remember that change takes time. The more you do it, the more natural it will become. Give yourself grace and keep engaging!

To work within a culture that is informed by community-engaged practices across each core of the CDCC. While the implementation of **community engagement** may vary based on the content area of the core, the principles of **equity**, honesty, trust, assurance, and mutual understanding will be core **principles** that guide our community engagement work.

Community engagement:

An ongoing process of building and nurturing relationships of mutual understanding and trust between communities and those seeking to connect with them, including liaising between [community partners](#) and larger systems.

To foster an environment in which all are welcomed at all stages and co-lead decision-making. This means partners, including academic and community partners, can not only express concerns and provide feedback but also engage in strategic planning and initiate new opportunities to improve the impact of the CDCC and RADx-UP-affiliated projects.

Community engagement is an ongoing process of building and nurturing relationships of mutual understanding and trust between communities and those seeking to connect with them, including liaising between community partners and larger systems.

Fostering a culture of trust and engaging communities in research is a foundational tenet of the RADx-UP Coordination and Data Collection Center (CDCC).

Foster a culture of trust and engagement of communities in research by:

- Prioritizing community-engaged work
- Strengthening information and resource sharing between academic institutions & community organizations
- Building and nurturing relationships of mutual understanding and trust
- Recognizing that community engagement is an ongoing process

These principles serve as core beliefs which should help center the work, interactions, and decisions of each core.

promote

Promote the long-term sustainability & success of RADx-UP CDCC initiatives.

create

Create opportunities to listen, learn, and inform.

engage

Engage without fear of judgment or retaliation.

provide

Provide opportunities for reflective conversations.

embrace

Embrace individual differences.

empower

Empower diverse communities.

Values vs. Principles¹⁵

VALUES are qualities or standards of behavior.	PRINCIPLES are rules or beliefs governing one's behavior.
Values help to form principles.	Principles are based on one's values.
Qualities	Rules

RADx-UP CDCC Values

As reflected above, values are qualities **or** standards of behavior that help inform an individual's or organization's principles. The CDCC has identified six **values** which inform the principles that guide the work.

In the pages that follow, the framework explores each of the values a little deeper, focusing on:

- Why the value is important
- Best practices to support incorporation in your workstream

equity

transparency

trust

respect

mutual understanding

accountability

EQUITY

ensures that all people can grow, contribute, and develop, regardless of their identity. When done right, it removes the barriers that marginalized groups often experience.

BEST PRACTICES

Integrate the perspectives and feedback of partners into decision-making processes

Help or encourage colleagues to be reflective and action-oriented about building a culture that is inclusive and supports the unique needs of partners

Share responsibility for outcomes

Treat all stakeholders with integrity and respect

Share decision-making and leadership as often as possible

Prioritize the expertise of stakeholders and partners most affected by inequities when identifying challenges and developing sustainable solutions

Allocate adequate resources

TRANSPARENCY

enables co-creation and innovation in environments where missteps are seen as opportunities to learn.

BEST PRACTICES^{18,25}

Clarify the reason why

- Provide ample context and/or background to support the request, process, change, etc.
- Use SBAR to help communicate clearly in email:
 - **Situation** (a concise statement of the problem)
 - **Background** (pertinent and brief information related to the situation)
 - **Assessment** (analysis and considerations of options — what you found/think)
 - **Request/Recommendation** (action requested/recommended — what you want)

Be clear about what information is needed and what needs to be shared

- Share useful insights and learnings to support effective decisions.
- Provide information that helps evaluate progress and outcomes (*i.e., criteria, metrics, outcomes, etc.*)
- Recognize that information reduces uncertainty
- Draft and share meeting minutes.

Create a coherent, accessible system for information storage

- Choose user friendly tools.
- Clearly define what should be stored & how long.
- Provide structures to support the system.
- Designate deadlines and responsible parties.
- Evaluate periodically for relevance.

Communicate openly about motives, resources, power dynamics, and decision-making processes

Acknowledge challenges and limitations and work openly to address these and maintain partners' or stakeholders' trust

TRUST

enhances teamwork, collaboration, and decision-making. It improves organizational alignment, efficiency, engagement, production, innovation, and creativity. Trust increases loyalty and retention and decreases stress and burnout.

BEST PRACTICES^{19,20,22}

Listen more than you speak: Focus on others

Cultivate an environment where you:

- Encourage your team to speak honestly and often.
- Engage in [active listening](#).
- Don't just think about how something benefits you, but also how others may benefit or be harmed.

Solicit and act on feedback

- Solicit feedback in different ways.
- Follow through on feedback.

Empower your team by trusting them first

- Be supportive without hovering.
- Provide opportunities for professional development.
- Invite team members to sit in on meetings that may be well-suited to their skills and/or strengths.

Create an inclusive culture

- Value and accept the strengths and unique qualities of your team.
- Build a team that evokes diversity in thought and practices.

Take a collaborative approach

- Be willing to work with others.
- Create joint goals and approaches.

Recognize that non-verbal communication is just as important as verbal communication

- Pay attention when someone is speaking. This isn't the time to check email or work on items for your next meeting.
- Display positive body language.

Focus on relational, not transactional, interactions

- Approach each interaction as if it will be one of many.

Make transparency a habit

- Speak honestly.
- Disclose information (good & bad).
- Ask and encourage questions.
- Be realistic.

Be consistent

- Follow through on your commitments.
- Say what you mean and mean what you say.
- Don't expect of your team what you don't expect of yourself.

Show appreciation

- Send thank you messages.
- Acknowledge when someone has done something

RESPECT

is a way for all people to know they are valued for their achievements, abilities, and qualities. Being valued and treated respectfully helps promote a positive work culture in which employees are fulfilled, loyal, engaged, and motivated to perform at their very best.

BEST PRACTICES^{26,27}

Extend grace

Empathize and be considerate of others.

Lead by example

- Do what you say.
- Follow up and follow through.
- Be reliable.
- Praise more than you criticize.

Speak up

If you see disrespectful or unsafe behavior that undermines the work environment, speak up.

Say thank you

Make sure people know you appreciate them and their actions.

Be clear about expectations

Listen

Listen to what everyone has to say.

Affirm people's opinions

Apologize

If you make a mistake, take responsibility and have a corrective action plan.

Celebrate together

Participate in activities with your team.

Acknowledge

Recognize the strengths & accomplishments of others.

Look for common ground

MUTUAL UNDERSTANDING

leads to respect for core interests and major concerns, expands consensus and common interests, and tempers differences. These are the foundations for a long-term healthy, stable relationship.

BEST PRACTICES^{23,24}

Focus on individual and shared needs

Ask the following questions:

- What does my colleague/partner need?
- What does my colleague/partner want?
- What is most important to them?
- What is least important to them?

Find common ground

Strengthen your partnerships

Internal partnerships

- **Form.** Provide opportunities for team building. Include the team in goal setting & task planning.
- **Storm.** Develop a plan & stick with it. Address conflict & help the team work through it.
- **Norm.** Don't lose sight of the goal.
- **Perform.** Offer resources & support throughout all stages.

External partnerships

Incorporate stages of CE continuum.

- Outreach. Consult. Involve. Collaborate. Share.

Engage in reflective conversations

- Focus on what the other person has to say and try to understand what they are trying to communicate through words, tone, and non-verbal cues.

- Practice paraphrasing and mirroring when speaking with others.
 - **Paraphrasing:** Listen to the speaker and use your own words to reflect what they said. This helps ensure you properly understand the message.
 - **Mirroring:** A shorter, simpler technique that requires you to repeat key parts of the message verbatim. This helps maintain focus throughout the conversation; shows that you are paying attention.

Build positive energy and goodwill

- Frame things positively.
- Create actionable items.
- Try to keep emotions out of your statements. (*I think...*)
- Take a break when you need it.
- Say what you mean and mean what you say.
- Create an environment where people can ask for clarification when needed without fear of ridicule or negative reprisal.
- Take a minute to see it from the other person's perspective.

A culture of self-

ACCOUNTABILITY

builds an environment where people acknowledge the impact of their actions, which builds trust, improves performance, strengthens culture, fosters greater commitment, and Increases morale.

BEST PRACTICES¹⁷

Respond when something is needed

- Acknowledge a request even if you can't address it immediately.
- Give an idea of when to expect receipt or final response.

Do what you agreed to do

- Complete action items by the deadline. Notify the team if you aren't able to complete it on time and provide an anticipated date of completion.
- Follow-up with involved parties to ensure everyone has what is needed.

Accept your share of the responsibility

- Make the hierarchy of accountability clear.
- Acknowledge shared accountability.

Create conditions that enable accountability to thrive

- Involve teams in decisions.
- Give people access to information.
- Create an environment where it is safe for people to disagree.

Explicitly delineate areas of responsibility

When responsibilities are unclear, it can lead to mistaken assumptions about who is responsible.

Build processes that are responsive to feedback from those we work with

Be willing to change and adapt throughout the process.

The words we use to describe our work should be clear and familiar to all CDCC staff. Because these terms are also commonly used in everyday language, it is important to define their specific meanings for our purposes. The following are the working definitions of terms used in this framework and throughout our work in the CDCC.

Active listening²: Listening to hear, understand, and retain information being shared with you. Requires you to pay attention, show you're listening, ask follow-up questions and provide feedback, and ask for clarification. *(Adapted from Colorado State University Global)*

Community: Group of people with shared identities, culture, language, values and/or interests. Members often come together to share experiences, thoughts, and ideas **or** to achieve a common mission. Communities may be virtual, geographically close, or in diaspora. *CDCC is a larger community made up of multiple smaller communities (cores, workstreams, roles, etc.).*

Community Advisory Board (CAB)³: Made up of community members with a shared identity, goal, geography, history, language, culture, and/or experience. Brought together to bring a community voice to an initiative, program, policy, or project. Ideally, they have the power and control to shape initiatives, programs, policies, or projects affecting their communities. *(Adapted from Urban Institute)*

Community-engaged research: Research partnership between institutions and communities that is mutually beneficial and incorporates shared decision-making and leadership between institutions and communities.

Community engagement: An ongoing process of building and nurturing relationships of mutual understanding and trust between communities and those seeking to connect with them, including liaising between community partners and larger systems.

Community partner⁴: Individuals, groups, and organizations from the public and private sectors that directly serve the local community; typically, these partners are not from within academic institutions. *(Adapted from Ole Miss)*

Dissemination⁵: Targeted distribution of information and materials through a variety of channels. Goal is to spread knowledge and share evidence-based interventions. *(AHRQ)*

Equality^{6,7}: Individuals or groups are given the same resources and opportunities, which can increase inequities in communities. By disregarding an individual's or community's actual needs or circumstances, it can hinder their ability to thrive. *(George Washington University; United Way)*

Equity^{6,7}: Recognizes that communities have different circumstances and needs, which must be taken into consideration when allocating resources and opportunities to help achieve equal outcomes. According to the 2019 Design in Tech Report, *"Equity is a solution for addressing imbalanced social systems. Justice can take equity one step further by fixing the systems in a way that leads to long-term, sustainable, equitable access for generations to come." Equity begins by meeting communities where they are.* *(George Washington University; United Way)*

Ethics⁸: The principles of conduct governing an individual or a group. *(Merriam Webster)*

Institutional racism⁹: Intentional or unintentional policies, practices, procedures, and/or outcomes within institutions that exclude or lead to poorer outcomes for people of color. *(Race Forward)*

Focus group^{8,10,11}: Research technique used to collect data through group interaction. Consists of a small group of purposefully selected people whose responses are studied and used to help determine the response that can be expected from a larger population. Used to identify and explore how people think, feel and behave.

Framework: Tool that illustrates shared language and understanding. Serves as a guide to support the implementation of ideas, beliefs, or rules in an organization. Typically intended for internal use.

Health equity¹²: This occurs when all people have the opportunity to attain the highest level of health. No one is kept from reaching the highest level of health because of their social position (e.g., class, immigration status) or social identities (e.g., race, gender, sexual orientation). Reflected in differences in length of life, quality of life, disease rates, disability, the severity of disease, access to treatment, and death. *(Adapted from CDC)*

Health ethics^{13,14}: Promotes the consideration of values in the prioritization and justification of actions by health professionals, researchers, and policymakers that may impact the health and well-being of patients, families, and communities. (WHO)

Core principles of healthcare ethics:
(Vermont Ethics Network)

- *Autonomy*: Honor the patient's right to make their own decision
- *Beneficence*: Help the patient advance his/her good
- *Nonmaleficence*: Do no harm
- *Justice*: Duty to be fair in how care is provided and in how resources are allocated

Partners: Individuals, communities, and/or organizations that enter into a mutual agreement to achieve a shared goal(s). These may include but are not limited to internal and external contacts: local, state, national, public, private, academic, faith- and community-based organizations, and internal staff. Partners may **or** may not be directly affected by the activities in which they engage. Unlike stakeholders, they take an active role in the work whether **or** not they are directly affected by the activities' outcomes. (Ex. American Institute for Research (AIR) is a CDCC partner.)

Partnerships: Relationships that typically involve close collaboration between parties with specified objectives, rights, and responsibilities. These collaborations build on the strengths and capabilities of each party. Should add value that exceeds what partners could achieve alone to allow for larger, more sustainable impacts.

Principles¹⁵: Rules or beliefs that govern our actions.

Social justice¹⁶: Fair and equitable division of resources, opportunities, and privileges in society. It involves efforts to end systemic violence, racism, and systems that devalue the dignity and humanity of any person (*John Lewis Institute for Social Justice*). This concept is aspirational and guides policies and practices that aim to bring conditions toward a vision of equity.

Stakeholders: Individuals, communities, or organizations that are invested in, affect, or are affected by a system, intervention, or program. Specifically, RADx-UP stakeholders include:

- The individuals or groups most affected by COVID-19 inequities, such as members of a local community.
- Individuals or organizations whose jobs or lives both might affect or be affected by processes, interventions, and/or programs.
- Institutions and their representatives who oversee and make decisions about the research and intervention processes & guidelines (*i.e., NIH or the CDCC*).

Structural racism⁹: As defined by *Race Forward*, racial inequities across institutions, policies, social structures, history, and culture. Deeply embedded in the economic, political, and legal systems. (*Race Forward*)

Values¹⁵: Qualities or standards that govern the behavior of a person.

